

Silver Nano Particles and their Applications: Review on Members of Meliaceae

Anitha S^{1*}, Lakshmi Priya M².

Author Affiliations

¹Dr. Anitha S, Department of Biotechnology, Sri Krishnadevaraya University, Anantapur-515 003, Andhra Pradesh, India

²Research Scholar, Department of Biotechnology, Sri Krishnadevaraya University, Anantapur-515 003, Andhra Pradesh, India

*Corresponding Author Email: anithasku@gmail.com

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Abstract: Nanotechnology is one of the fascinating branches of science with many applications. In this field synthesis of Silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) are having wider range of applications regarding Metal based nanoparticles. Silver itself is having antimicrobial effect and when it is combined with the Plant extract form Green nanoparticles. Scientists are using these nanoparticles in multidisciplinary fields such as medicinal, industrial and environmental purposes. The present review gives information of the synthesis and applications of the Meliaceae members. The present paper covers all the research done till now and can help the research community to take further studies.

Keywords: Silver nanoparticles, antimicrobial effect, Plant extract.

Introduction

Nanotechnology is an advanced field of science that make use of nano particles (0.1-100nm) with unique physical and chemical characteristics. Oberdorster et al. [1] stressed the need to know the risk and benefits about the Nanoparticles application. Hasan [2] has published a review on the nanoparticle synthesis and their types. Nanoparticles (NPs) can be of various types like Carbon based, Ceramic type, Polymers, Semiconductors, Lipid based and metals [3]. Carbon based are Fullerenes and carbon nanotubes [4, 5]. Ceramic NPs are inorganic solids [6], while semiconductor NPs are between metal and non-metals [7, 8]. Polymeric NPs are organic based ones [9, 10]. Lipid moieties comes under lipid based NPs [11, 12]. Metal type are purely of metals like copper, silver and gold. Metal type and size of the particles influences the properties of these nano particles [13]. Silver nano particles (AgNPs) are having, unique features like high surface to volume ratio, electrical conductivity, optical and thermal properties, when compared with different types of NPs and other metals, so they are widely used in medical field [14, 15]. Kim et al. [15] undertaken a case study to know about the risk evaluation of silver nanoparticle when exposed from antibacterial sprays. Because of wide range of application of AgNPs, risk evaluation studies are must. They finally concluded that AgNPs are having lower risk to no risk levels. Therefore they are now used in a number of consumer products [15, 16].

Inhibitory effect of Silver on microorganisms was also stressed by [17, 18]. Morones et al. [17] reported that silver nanoparticles can anchor and penetrate into gram negative cell wall which then leads to increased cell permeability and cell death. This nature of silver is due to the free radical formation [19]. Regarding the synthesis of AgNPs was present by Iravani et al. [20]. In present paper a review is present regarding the synthesis and applications of Meliaceae members. Khan et al. [21] for the first time reported Silver nanoparticle synthesis using *Azadirachta indica*, leaf extract. For the

characterization of these particles they have used UV-Visible spectroscopy, selected area electron diffraction (SAED) and Transmission electron microscopy.

Kathiravan et al. [22] reported silver nanoparticles synthesis using *Melia dubia* leaf extract and tested against in vitro cancer cell lines. Joany et al. [23] reported AgNPs synthesis using Neem leaf extract. They have characterised these particles using UV-Visible spectroscopy, SEM (Scanning Electron Microscopy), EDAX or EDX (Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy) and Fluorescence spectroscopy. They have reported the particle size as 43.23nm.

Sajeshkumar et al. [24] reported the synthesis of silver nanoparticles using *A. indica* leaf extract and its antibacterial activity. These researchers used UV-Vis spectroscopy, SEM-EDX for the characterization of developed 146nm AgNPs. They have used *Klebsiella* species and *Escherichia coli* (2 gram negative bacteria and *Bacillus* species, *Micrococcus* species and *Staphylococcus* species (3 gram positive) bacteria for their study and reported antimicrobial activity.

Ahmed et al. [25] developed AgNPs using *A. indica* with aqueous leaf extract. They used UV-Visible spectrophotometer, TEM (Transmission electron microscopy) to identify the size shape and morphology of nanoparticles. Performed DLS (dynamic light scattering) for size measurement of synthesized AgNPs and found to be 34nm. Later used FTIR (Fourier transform Infrared spectroscopy) analysis for confirming the dual role of plant extract as a capping agent and reducing agent. They have tested these nanoparticles for antimicrobial activity using *S. aureus* and *E. coli* and found to have the ability of antimicrobial nature.

Mehmood et al. [26] used *Melia azedarach* leaf extract for synthesizing the AgNPs and Characterized using SEM, EDX and UV-Visible spectroscopy. They reported the particle size as 34-48 nm with more antibacterial activity against *E. coli*, *Klebsiella pneumonia* than *S. aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Proteus spp.* Jebarubi et al. [27] reported the synthesis of AgNPs using *M. azedarach* leaf extract and characterized these using FT-IR, X-RD and SEM analysis. They have reported 2-20 µm silver particle size.

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

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